

Three strands of explanations on root causes of civil war in low-income and weak states in sub-Saharan Africa: Implications for education

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ABSTRACT

This paper is a theoretical exploration of the relationship between schooling and the root causes of contemporary conflicts in low-income and weak states in sub-Saharan Africa. It does so by exploring three predominant theoretical strands on contemporary intrastate conflict and their implications to education: (1) the 'grievance' explanation; (2) an alternative economic explanation, focusing on the idea of the 'opportunity cost of rebellion'; and (3) a political explanation that shows the role of the ruling elites and the state. The article suggests some theoretical and conceptual insights on examining the ways in which education fuels into the root causes of conflict in low-income and weak states.

Keywords: Education and conflict Contemporary conflict Theory Interdisciplinary approach Civil war Low-income countries Weak states Sub-Saharan Africa Greed versus grievances

1. Introduction

Most of contemporary internal conflict takes the form of a civil war where the government of a state is one of the warring parties, and it has primarily emerged in low-income and 'weak' states in sub-Saharan Africa. Collier et al. (2003) show that low-income countries (defined as having a per capita annual income below US\$745) face 15 times higher risk of civil war than the countries of the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), which face only a negligible risk of civil war. Many contemporary civil wars also have taken place in 'weak' states (Berdal and Malone, 2000; World Bank, 2011). Measuring governance with general rule of law and government effectiveness, low corruption, and strong protection of human rights, Fearon (2010) finds that countries with above average governance indicators for their income level have between 30 and 45 percent lower risk of civil conflict outbreaking within the next 5–10 years. Although the number of major conflicts are in a decline since the early 1990s (World Bank, 2011), there is a high risk for re-occurrence in countries once affected by conflict. The World Development Report 2011 states that 90% of the civil wars during the last decade took place in countries that had already experienced a civil war in the past 30 years (World Bank, 2011). The article focuses on the link between such conflicts and education, more specifically, the formal schooling provided by the state.¹ Knowing how formal schooling can contribute to conflict in such contexts is the first step to avoid education augmenting the already high risk of (re)lapsing into conflict.

It is widely acknowledged that the nature of conflict in Africa has been changing since the end of the Cold War (e.g. Cilliers and Schunemann, 2013; Straus, 2012; World Bank, 2011). Although civil

¹ By 'education' in this article, I only refer to the form of formal schooling provided by the state in this review, although this does not mean by any means that other forms of education and training are relevant to conflict (see, for example, Brock, 2011; Pagen, 2011; Hammond, 1998). It is simply that there is no scope for the article to deal with other forms of education.

wars remain the predominant form of conflicts in Africa, the lines between criminal violence, political violence, and conflict are becoming increasingly ambiguous (Cilliers and Schunemann, 2013; World Bank, 2011). In Sierra Leone, for instance, rebels and the government army had increasingly recruited a fluid but essentially the same group of marginalised youth, who switched sides at their convenience (see Keen, 2005; SLTRC, 2004). Straus (2012) summarises the nature of today's conflict as "Today's wars are typically fought on the peripheries of states, and insurgents tend to be militarily weak and factionalized" (p. 181). The end of the Cold War also meant the loss of external funding from superpower rivalries. For armed groups, accessing and controlling high value natural resources becomes an important part of securing funding for themselves and perpetuating the conflict (e.g. UNEP, 2006). This also relates to the downscaling of conflicts, because the fighting groups do not have the strength to launch a large-scale fight nor to challenge the dominant party in capital. The 'resource-based insurgencies' also have strong transnational characteristics economically, politically and in terms of fighting forces. They rely on illicit trade of resources and arms (Cilliers and Schunemann, 2013; Berdal and Malone, 2000) and the fighters move around countries joining different rebel movements (Hoffman, 2011). As such, even though they are called 'civil wars' which by definition means an internal conflict, the current conflicts are often regionalised and internationalised.

There have been lively debates over the root causes and risk factors to contemporary civil conflicts in the last decades to understand the changing nature of conflicts (e.g. Kaplan, 1994; Huntington, 1996; Berdal and Malone, 2000; Collier and Hoeffler, 2000, 2004). It has become clear that these new forms of conflict are not fully comprehensible in the traditional models or under the common assumptions of civil war. Traditionally civil war, for one, has been presented as a contest of two competing professional armies, civilians being bystanders. And these two competing armies are presented as each, homogeneous group, seeking to "win the war" and "defeat the enemy" (Keen, 2000, p. 26). It has also been portrayed to be driven by political grievances and aim, which is to take control of the state (Keen, 2000). However, civil wars in low-income and weak states were not in many cases a simple contest between two sides, either rebels versus government forces or between two rival ethnic groups, as discussed above. It has also come to be recognised that economic dimensions of conflict 'war economies' are essential in fully understanding the nature – as well as political ideologies and grievances – (see Keen, 1998; Reno, 1998; Collier and Hoeffler, 1998; Berdal and Malone, 2000).²

Education has an important role to play in such conflicts. On the one hand, education or training is seen as a way to meaningfully engage youth and to reduce the conflict risks. There is a growing concern, evident in the way in which international donor assistance is increasingly tied to security agendas (Novelli, 2010). Youth are often the largest population cohort in weak states or conflict-affected countries and leaving them 'idle' by failing to provide them with education or training if not employment may increase the risks of social and political instability (World Bank, 2006, 2009; Matsumoto, 2011). However, education can also be a factor that fuels violent conflict. Education has often appeared as a relevant factor to contemporary conflict (e.g. Collier and Hoeffler, 2000, 2004; Thyne, 2006; Barakat and Urdal, 2009; Stewart, 2002b; Richards, 1996; Keen, 2005). Education is discussed there as a factor that can increase the risk as well as reducing it. There have also been more and more studies in the field of education and conflict focusing on the link of education to the root causes and pathways to contemporary conflict, engaging with the literature above (Smith, 2005; Novelli and Cardozo, 2008; Ostby and Urdal, 2010; Hilker, 2010; Brown, 2010; King, 2014; Burde, 2014). In particular, Ostby and Urdal (2010) identified the theoretical propositions related to levels, expansion and inequality to education and examined the empirical data available for each of the various propositions about connection between education and

² This is not to say that economic interests implied in conflicts have not been acknowledged in earlier literature or in other types of conflicts.

conflict. In turn King (2014), focusing on Rwanda, identified theoretically the pathways through which education intertwines with the root causes and development of identity-based conflicts.

Nevertheless, our theoretical and conceptual understanding of how education can play into the root causes of conflicts in low-income and weak states is still limited and the strengthening of this aspect is seen as necessary to further solidify the field (Rappleye and Paulson, 2007; Davies, 2005). Therefore, building on the literature above, this article focuses primarily on two tasks. First, identifying the features of education in relationship to other conditions in society articulated in the available theories on the root causes of conflict. Many agree that education alone does not instigate conflict (e.g. Hilker, 2010; Arlow, 2004; Gurr, 1970), and yet, the existing literature has tended to point out isolated features of the educational system – e.g. curriculum, access issues – treating them as independent indicators (see Matsumoto, 2015). We need to be able to articulate the conditions that ‘activate’ the connection: understand not only what kind of educational provision is relevant to conflict but when it becomes relevant. Second, it suggests the areas or units of analysis that should be examined (in depth) in current theoretical accounts in order to understand more comprehensively the ways in which education might be fuelling the root causes of conflict. The limited available knowledge implies that the provision of education, even if it is seen as a key tool to promote peace, stability and development, might be fuelling a (second) cycle of conflict there without realising this. As mentioned above, low-income and weak states (that have been affected by conflict) are considered to have a high risk of (re)lapsing into a cycle of conflict and we need to understand the role of education in this increased risk.

The article will explore the relationship of formal schooling to the root causes, defined as initial factors and circumstances that fuel conflict, among all the pathways in which education may contribute to conflict. The article does not cover a whole range of contemporary conflict either, but focuses on civil wars in low-income and weak states in sub-Saharan Africa. Sub-Saharan Africa has been the scene of many civil wars; nearly 20 countries, or about 40 percent of the region, have experienced at least one, between 1960 and 2000 (Elbadawi and Sambanis, 2000). This is not to say that sub-Saharan African has more or longer conflicts compared to other regions of the world. On the contrary, as said above, conflict in this region is reducing and less frequent. However, it is the continent where a significant change in the nature of conflict is being witnessed and thereby many scholarly debates making reference to the region (e.g. Kaplan, 1994; Berdal and Malone, 2000; Keen, 1998; Collier and Hoeffler, 2000, 2004). Also the article focuses on the form of civil war as a ‘discrete category’ although, as recognised above, many of the civil wars are regionalised and internationalised. We still need to deepen our understanding of contemporary internal conflict; there are issues in and about the country that might account for when a civil war not only breaks out but also perpetuates in one country but does not do so in another country. For instance, referring to the case of civil war in Sierra Leone, Keen (2005) states that ‘[i]f the war sometimes resembled a virus spreading from Liberia, it was the weakness of the Sierra Leonean “body” that allowed it to spread so quickly and widely’ (p. 58). Understanding and tackling the issues within the country will help it become more resistant to the external risk factors.

The article explores in depth three major strands of theories on the root causes of contemporary civil war in low-income and weak states. The exploration is deliberately selective focusing on the conceptual discussion of this particular aspect of the education and conflict connection. The first strand of the explanations represents the ‘grievance’ approach, a conventional explanation of conflict, and mainly draws on the idea of ‘horizontal inequalities (HIs)’ by Stewart (e.g. 2008a) and ‘relative deprivation’ by Gurr (1970). While Gurr (1970) is seen as a ‘classic’ approach explaining political grievances as a primary cause of political violence, Stewart develops the idea further, explaining that grievances stem from horizontal inequalities in political, socioeconomic, and cultural arenas. The second strand is an alternative economic explanation. There I focus on the idea of ‘opportunity cost of rebellion’ by Collier and others (2000, 2004, 2009). Originally terming the

debate ‘Greed versus Grievances,’ Collier was the most prominent researcher to challenge the idea that political grievances are the primary root cause of violent conflict – on which HIs and relative deprivation are based. Collier’s theory and model allows examination of education as a factor that plays into rational choices of young people regarding whether taking up arms or not. The third is a political explanation that focuses on the role of the state and ruling elites in the emergence of civil war, drawing mainly from Bates and Reno. While Stewart’s and Collier’s accounts focus on why insurgents take up arms, the political economic analysis of conflict of Bates and Reno reveals how the incumbent state-officials ‘prepared the field’ (2008, p. 131) for insurgents to take up arms against them. Although they do not discuss education as a factor that actively promoted state collapse or civil war, they introduce education as part of public services and the state institutions that the ruling elites came to neglect deliberately.

For all three strands, I first describe their main concepts and implications and later critically examine and elaborate these in relation to education. The paper does not test the general validity of each explanation, rather more specifically, the article attempts to unpack essential theoretical and conceptual insights on the ways in which education plays into the root causes that the existing literature may have been largely overlooking. Given the specific aim of the article, some explanations of contemporary conflict that do not have direct relevance to education are not taken up here, for example, the ‘green war’ theory (Homer-Dixon, 1994) and the role of natural resources in conflict (e.g. Ross, 2004).

2. The ‘Grievance’ approach: horizontal inequalities and relative deprivation

2.1. Main ideas of HIs and relative deprivation

The horizontal inequalities of Stewart and the relative deprivation theory of Gurr can be seen as fundamental and complementary theories in understanding the role of grievances in civil war. While Stewart’s theory focuses on how objective inequalities among groups of people can fuel their collective frustrations, and ultimately conflict, Gurr’s theory is concerned with people’s perceptions of deprivation. And, while Stewart’s theory explains the group dynamics behind identity based conflict, Gurr’s idea helps understand people’s sense of grievances in contexts where ‘ethnicity’ or cultural groups did not become key to the conflict, such as in Sierra Leone and in Liberia.

The concept of horizontal inequalities (HIs) refers to inequalities between cultural groups³ (Stewart, 2002b). Stewart argues that when the HIs are sharp and multidimensional HIs may arouse deep resentment between cultural groups and lead to violent struggles (Stewart, 2008a). In other words, cultural group differences on their own do not cause conflict but only become salient when they coincide with socioeconomic and political inequalities (Stewart, 2002a). Stewart distinguishes HIs from what she terms vertical inequalities, or inequalities among individuals, arguing that, violent conflict occurs when a group is mobilised, not individuals (e.g. 2002b). In Stewart’s theory, two points will become important to unravel the relationship of education to conflict in the following section: (1) HIs are prone to intersect with violent conflict when they are multidimensional as well as being sharp; (2) the extent to which each element may become relevant to violent conflict depends on the extent to which the element holds ‘social significance’ (e.g. Stewart, 2008a). Social significance relates to how the element influences one’s behaviour, income and well-being. Therefore, when an element matters to people it can be salient to political mobilisation in one society, but may not in others if it does not hold social significance there. Stewart (e.g. 2008a) further explains that the social significance of the element can be found in its innate value or in its instrumentality for achieving other goals, such as incomes and well-being.

³ The cultural groups include ethnic, religious, and regional groups, as well as caste, class, and race among other things.

Stewart's theory is useful in understanding the root causes of conflict that have taken the form of identity-based conflicts in low-income and weak states and beyond. Many contemporary wars grapple with ethnic or religious tensions, and Stewart has identified the inequalities among groups as the fundamental underlying cause.⁴ Some have criticised the relevance of inequalities to civil war based on the statistical insignificance of individual inequalities in cross-national studies (e.g. Collier and Hoeffler, 2004), but Stewart, by distinguishing HIs from vertical inequalities, not only defended the relevance of inequalities to conflict but also clarified the kinds of inequalities that are relevant. At the same time, the idea of HIs is a hypothesis that is yet to be satisfactorily confirmed or rejected.⁵ It should also be recognised that there are a few ambiguities in Stewart's idea of HIs. For instance, they do not explain cases where 'ethnic' or cultural group lines or inequalities among cultural groups did not become salient in war, as in the civil wars in Sierra Leone, Liberia or Mozambique. Another ambiguity is the explanation with regard to people's perception. Although Stewart recognises that perceived inequalities differ from the actual inequalities (Stewart, 2008b), she takes the position that perceptions reflect some reality, with her studies mainly relying on 'objective' HIs.

Gurr's theory of 'relative deprivation' centres on perceptions and helps explain cases where ethnicity or objective HIs did not become salient. Gurr explains that '[d]iscontent arising from the perception of relative deprivation' is the basic condition for the potential of collective violence (1970, p. 13, emphasis added). Gurr (1970) defines relative deprivation as a 'perceived discrepancy between men's value expectations and their value capabilities' (p. 13, emphases added). In a simple sense, relative deprivation is the perceived gap between 'ought,' i.e. what they should get, and 'is,' i.e. what they can get in reality. This means that discontent may not be about their position compared to that of others in society. It may arise from the perceived gap between their own past experiences and their actual capabilities in the present, as it is ultimately about a difference felt psychologically between people's expectations and their capabilities in reality. For example, Gurr's theory seems to elucidate the sense of deprivation and frustration felt by the college students who initially organised the 'revolution' which had led to the decade-long civil war in Sierra Leone. Some argue that young people were frustrated because the government would not provide public employment upon graduating from college as they believed it had used to do so to the 'older' generations (e.g. Krech and Maclure, 2003; Rashid, 2004). Gurr's theory makes it clear that the frustration was rooted in their sense of deprivation; their expectations were established based on the achievement of previous generations and yet their actual capabilities did not allow such expectations to be fulfilled.

2.2. HIs, relative deprivation and education

Stewart's theory of HIs clarifies the kind of educational inequalities that should be taken into account as well as the conditions that can make them relevant to conflict. First of all, she clarifies that it is educational inequalities among cultural groups, not among individuals, that are relevant to conflict. Second, educational inequalities among groups not only need to be sharp but at the same time there have to be sharp HIs in other areas and in the same direction. HIs are categorised into economic, social, political and cultural status HIs, and each dimension contains a number of elements. Education is incorporated as part of social HIs (Stewart, 2010, p. 2). The findings of the

⁴ It should also be noted that Stewart's theory does not explain all the pathways how HIs develop into an identity-based conflict. However, as I clarified at the beginning it is beyond the article's scope and the ways in which they do so and how education gets involved in the process is well documented elsewhere (e.g. King, 2014).

⁵ Due to a difficulty associated with obtaining data on HIs cross-nationally (Stewart, 2008b), the studies by her and her colleagues have mostly been quantitative country case studies. Collier and Hoeffler (2007) criticise this, saying that there is no empirical measure available to test Stewart's hypothesis in a crosssection of countries.

different functions of HIs by category in fuelling violent conflict illuminate the relationships of HIs among categories (see Stewart, 2008b). For one, they found that it is sharp social and economic HIs that increase the probabilities of conflict (Ostby, 2008). However, it is the nature of the political HIs that determine whether social and economic HIs lead to conflict (Langer and Ukiwo, 2008; Caumartin et al., 2008). Stewart (2008b) shows that a higher probability of conflict is found when the political and socioeconomic HIs are sharp and run in the same direction (Langer, 2008; Ukiwo, 2008). This suggests that, in particular, educational inequalities should be accompanied by political HIs as well as other social and economic HIs if they are to be relevant to conflict. If the political HIs run in the opposite direction, conflict may not occur even if there are sharp educational HIs and other social and economic HIs.

Third, the idea of social significance gives further sophistication to the kind of educational inequalities that could be relevant to conflict. In Stewart's explanation, an element needs to have social significance in order for HIs in that element to be relevant to a risk of violent conflict. If they do not, then HIs in that element will not frustrate people. This means that, whether educational HIs matter to a risk of conflict depends, first of all, on whether education carries social significance in a particular society. If it does, the next question to be examined is what kind or level of education holds this social significance and whether HIs exist in that level or kind of education. Even if there are inequalities in education at one level, e.g. in primary education, if that level of schooling does not hold social significance then such inequalities may not be significant in regard to the risk of violent conflict.

We also need to examine whether the social significance of education lies in the innate value or the instrumental value of the kind of education. Recall that the element can have social significance in itself or can be socially significant because of its instrumentality in achieving other goals, i.e. incomes or well-being. Education's innate value may refer to the importance of learning itself for the well-being of people in society, and the instrumental value of education may point to the value of educational qualifications, skills and knowledge as a means to acquiring higher income and improved social status. This is an important distinction to make. If education in its innate value holds social significance, then educational inequalities on their own, irrespective of the conditions of other sectors in society, can become relevant to the risk of violent conflict. However, if education is valued more instrumentally in the society in question, then, it requires further analysis. First, it requires an examination of the goals that people want to achieve through education. Then, we must determine the level and kind of education that is instrumental to these aspirations and whether inequalities exist there.

The idea of the instrumental value of education brings another aspect to consider in educational HIs' link to violent conflict. Inequalities in education are a source of tension in some societies (and violent conflict in some) precisely because the instrumental value of education is highly regarded (e.g. Ukiwo, 2007). Contrary to people's perceptions of the strong instrumental value of education, however, the returns on education, or the expected instrumentality of education, are contested particularly in developing countries; those who have been schooled to a higher level remain unemployed, such as in India (Jeffrey et al., 2008), Peru (Crivello, 2009) and African countries (World Bank, 2009; O'Brien, 1996). Whether education plays an expected instrumental role or not is an important issue for those who had access to the educational services and for considering the

link of their sense of grievances to a risk of conflict.⁶ It is at this point where Gurr's theory of relative deprivation becomes useful. He argues that education is a major source in raising aspirations (that is, increases value expectations). It puts children from traditional societies in motion towards new goals, by investing their time and energy in formal education. And yet if a person finds no available jobs or that their payment or political capabilities remain low upon receiving an education (that is, constrained value capabilities), the gap between expectations and capabilities becomes rather widened. The likely consequences of this, Gurr argues, are disillusionment and anger. However, as Stewart, Gurr (1970) notes that disillusionment and anger due to education on its own seldom lead to political violence; it is more likely when accompanied by pre-existing relative deprivation – one that is both intense and wide in scope – in the society.

Through the exploration of Stewart's and Gurr's theories, we can see the link between education, sense of grievances and risk of violent conflict more systematically and in relation to other conditions and circumstances of society. We have clarified, through the theory of Stewart, under what circumstances and what kind of inequalities in education can be relevant to conflict. The relative deprivation of Gurr elucidates fundamentally how education can arouse a sense of grievances and when it can lead to political violence. At the same time, as their theories are not 'education centred', understandably, some aspects related to educational processes remain underdeveloped. For one, Stewart's theory does not consider the special weight that inequalities in education may have in people's sense of grievances. Precisely because of the high instrumental value of education, educational inequalities have come to be perceived as a source of perpetuating socioeconomic inequalities in society (Stewart, 2008b). In that sense, inequalities in education could have a heavier weight in people's sense of grievances than other categories, which for example Ukiwo (2007) discussed in-depth for the case of Nigeria. Furthermore, Stewart does not explain all the pathways through which education gets involved in the development of an identity-based conflict (including raising ethnic tensions and divisions). However, these have been well articulated in the educational literature (e.g. King, 2014; Bush and Saltarelli, 2000; Ukiwo, 2007; Obura, 2008; Shields and Rappleye, 2008).

3. Economic explanations: the opportunity cost of rebellion and the youth bulge

3.1. The main ideas of the opportunity cost of rebellion and the youth bulge

In economic explanations, I centre on the idea of the opportunity cost of rebellion by Collier et al. and the youth bulge, a related theory. Collier and others (Collier and Hoeffler, 2000, 2004; Collier et al. 2009) argue that, for a civil war to emerge, the war has to be viable or profitable economically. One of the conditions under which a civil war can be viable or profitable is when there is an abundant source of cheap labour (whose opportunity cost is low) that will fight as rebels. Otherwise, the rebels as an organisation cannot (afford to) recruit enough labour for a rebellion to be actualised. This is what Collier et al.'s idea of the opportunity cost of rebellion is essentially about.⁷ An opportunity cost is a concept in the rational choice theory of economics that refers to the value of the next-highest-valued alternative use of that resource. An application of this concept to rebellion suggests that, for a person to join a rebellion, he or she cannot spend time doing something else. If his or her next-best alternative to joining the rebellion is working and earning money, the

⁶ Stewart is aware that inequalities in access to educational services may not be a good indication of inequalities in the benefits of outcomes. This can be seen when she made the distinction between inequalities in access to services and those in the benefits of outcome in conceptualising social HIs. Also, in Peru, it has been found that not only educational HIs exist at both levels (i.e. access to the provision and the returns), but the HIs are wider in the returns than at the level of provision (Figuroa, 2008). However, she does not refer to the possible effects of the differences on the risk of conflict.

⁷ Although Collier et al.'s argument has evolved over the years (c.f. Collier and Hoeffler, 1998, 2004; Collier et al., 2009), their idea of the opportunity cost of rebellion has been consistent.

opportunity cost of rebellion is the cost associated with joining the rebellion plus the money that is foregone by not working.

Behind Collier et al.'s idea of the opportunity cost lies the youth bulge theory. Youth bulge theory, simply put, claims that a large cohort of young males ('youth bulge') in the population increases the risk of political violence in society (e.g. Moller, 1968). The male secondary school enrolment rate⁸ is one of the three major 'proxies' employed to 'measure' the opportunity cost of rebellion, together with income per capita and the growth rate of the economy (Collier and Hoeffler, 2000, 2004). The rationale behind this is that young males are the group from which the rebels are the most recruited, and the average number of years they have been in school affects their income-earning opportunities and the opportunity cost of rebellion; if the male secondary enrolment rate is higher (which means that many males are accessing the level of schooling), the opportunity cost of rebel labour is higher and thus the risk of civil war is lower.⁹ I come back to this later.

The model developed by Collier et al. using cross-national quantitative datasets as well as their theory sparked much discussion in the studies of contemporary conflict and contributed to advance the field. At the same time, some major shortcomings of the theory and the model should be recognised here. First of all, its simplicity. Collier and Hoeffler (2004) made a dichotomous claim – greed over grievances –, purely based on an economic calculation. Some researchers argue that contemporary conflict is much more complex, and for a conflict to emerge, it is not a dichotomous question of 'either-or,' but different factors including grievances are intertwined and at work (Ballentine and Nitzchke, 2005; Keen, 2000). The ambiguity of the construction of 'proxies' in Collier et al.'s model has also been commented. For instance, they use the income per capita as a proxy for the opportunity cost. However, it is essentially about the poverty of nations (Guichaua, 2010) and does not suggest the number or concentration of poor people within countries, which seems to be a more appropriate measure of the opportunity cost (Humphreys, 2003). Indeed, the same variable, income per capita, is used as a proxy for state strength by Fearon and Laitin (2003). In relation to this, even though the concept of the opportunity cost alludes to the individual level, his evidence is only on the country level; using the macroeconomic approach, he infers motivation (in the focus on 'greed') from observational proxies and measures the costs and benefits at the organisational level, looking at the rebels as a single agent. Nevertheless, the theory and the model of Collier et al. are useful to examine education as a factor that plays into the rational choices of young people to whether take up arms or not, which I analyse more closely in the following section.

3.2. Opportunity cost of rebellion, youth bulges, and education

Putting aside their use of male secondary school enrolment as a proxy for a moment, as a theory Collier et al. suggest the importance of determining, first, the level of education that is most relevant to increase the future income prospect of young males in the country. Then, determine to what extent the level of education is available. When a level of formal education that is most relevant to increase the future income prospect of young males in the country is not available to the majority, the majority has a low opportunity cost to enlist as rebels and this as a result increases the risk of conflict. As such, it is the (un)availability of that level of education, not any other, that determines the opportunity cost of rebellion.

⁸ The enrolment rate is measured as the gross enrolment ratios (GER), i.e. the ratio of total enrolment regardless of age to the population of the age group that officially corresponds to the level of education shown.

⁹ Collier et al. have also tested the significance of youth bulge proxies themselves, but the empirical results are mixed. Collier and Hoeffler (2004) did not find either the proportion of young men aged between 15 and 29 in the population or the population density to be significant factors, whereas Collier et al. (2009) found that the proportion of young men in the population does increase the risk of civil war.

In their empirical studies, however, Collier et al. focus on the relevance of the male secondary school enrolment rate to conflict. They assume that it is the level that is relevant to the opportunity cost of rebellion. They argue this for two reasons. One is that the secondary schooling increases the employability to follow (Collier and Hoeffler, 2000; Chauvet and Collier, 2007). In other words, when young males do not have a secondary education, their income will be unusually low and thus the economic opportunity cost of rebellion is suggested as low. The other reason is that secondary schooling occupies youths while they are in school: 'when young men lack something to occupy them the risk of trouble is increased' (Chauvet and Collier, 2007, p. 7). In this sense, secondary schooling (rather than the primary) is the relevant level of schooling that occupies the young men. Employing male secondary school enrolment rate, based on this rationale, as one of the three proxies to measure the opportunity cost of rebellion, Collier and Hoeffler (2000, 2004) find that the opportunity cost of rebellion is statistically significant when the regression model was run separately. Through this finding, they conclude that a higher opportunity cost has substantial effects on reducing the risk of conflict, but recognising a statistical issue in the finding.¹⁰

Collier et al.'s hypothesis or assumption of the relevance of the secondary school enrolment rate to the risk of conflict is confirmed by other studies that have taken up a similar methodology, using cross-national quantitative datasets. The study that most thoroughly investigates the relationship is Barakat and Urdal (2009); they find that a large proportion of the population being young males is likely to increase the risk of conflict in societies where male secondary education enrolment is low. Furthermore, the combined effect of low education (i.e. male secondary school enrolment), and a large proportion of young males in the population on the risk of conflict is found to be greater in low and middle-income countries. Similarly, Thyne (2006) finds that the higher school enrolment rates (primary enrolment rate, secondary enrolment rate, and male secondary enrolment rate), the lower the probability of civil war. And among the three types of enrolment rates tested, the male secondary education enrolment rate is found to have the strongest effect.

However, the relevance of male secondary school enrolment rate to the risk of conflict, and whether its relevance to the risk of conflict can be explained by the idea of opportunity cost of rebellion, are yet to be demonstrated. On one hand, African country case studies that have been conducted based on Collier and Hoeffler's (2004) model (Collier and Sambanis, 2005) are broadly consistent with the hypothesis; countries that have experienced civil war, e.g. Mali, Senegal, or Sudan, have had a low male secondary school enrolment rate. However, Eastern European and Middle Eastern country cases contradict the statistical finding on the relevance of male secondary school enrolment rate to the risk of conflict (Collier and Sambanis, 2005). That is, countries that have had high enrolment rates of education, e.g. Yugoslavia, Georgia, Russia or Lebanon, have experienced civil war. For instance, Lebanon has achieved one of the highest literacy rates in the Arab world (60% adult literacy rate) and yet has experienced one of the longest civil wars. This can be seen in contrast to Saudi Arabia, which has an extremely low secondary schooling rate (4%) but has not experienced civil war (Sambanis, 2005). Interpreting regional differences in the results, Sambanis (2005) suggests there is a different path from education increasing the opportunity cost of enlisting as rebels as Collier and Hoeffler (2004) argue. That is the inculcation of a nationalist ideology in schooling; education can be used to mobilise support for conflict, particularly in countries where education is sectarian as in Lebanon. This line of argument has also been well argued in education and conflict literature (see Davies, 2004; Bush and Saltarelli, 2000), and the potential role of education in 'changing attitudes' (p. 569) is also acknowledged in Collier and Hoeffler (2004). As

¹⁰ The male secondary education enrolment rate and per capita income are highly correlated and as a result these two variables cannot be used in the same regression model ($p = 0.8$). Therefore, they limit themselves to say that "[t]he evidence is thus consistent with the hypothesis that the more educated is a society the less prone is it to war, but falls short of demonstrating that this is the case" (Chauvet and Collier, 2007, p. 7).

far as the article is concerned we may say that the country case studies do not contradict the statistical finding as it is concerned with low-income and weak states in sub-Saharan Africa.

A fundamental question regarding the opportunity cost of rebellion explanation still remains: is the opportunity cost of rebellion that Collier et al. argue an appropriate interpretation of the empirical finding that higher enrolment rate reduces the probability of conflict? It may possibly mean, rather than the opportunity cost, that a large majority of young males is critical to the propaganda of the war as a result of being longer in school and learning how to examine information more critically. As a result, they are less vulnerable to manipulation and less likely to enlist as rebels (e.g. Davies, 2004). One of the two effects of secondary schooling on increasing the opportunity cost of rebellion that Collier et al. point out above are somewhat ambivalent. To reiterate, the two effects are the meaningful engagement of young men while they are in secondary school (by engaging in school related activities every day) and that schooling increasing the later employability. There is not much to argue against the first effect. However, the logic behind the second effect needs critical scrutiny. The contention that secondary schooling increases future income is debatable in the reality of developing countries, as I have discussed above. That is, the returns on education, or the instrumentality of education that people perceive and expect in achieving other goals, i.e. incomes or well-being, are in reality contested, leaving many of those who have been schooled to a higher level unemployed. However, what Collier et al. suggest is taking for granted education's instrumental value; in other words, their theory assumes that secondary schooling increases employability of those who complete the level of schooling. At the same time, a relevant point of concern may be the perceptions and expectations of young males. Regardless of whether the premise functions in reality, if young males perceive that their schooling increases future income prospects, then the perception already may mean that the opportunity cost of enlisting as rebels is increased.

As such, the idea that education increases the opportunity cost of rebellion, and thus reduces the risk of violent conflict, has opened up the exploration of the role of education in violent conflict beyond the premise of grievances as its primary cause. Further, Collier et al.'s ideas suggest that general lack or scarcity of provision of schooling can also fuel the root causes of conflict, not only the objective inequalities in the provision as suggested by Stewart. And yet the links among school enrolment rate, the opportunity cost of rebellion explanation, and the risk of violent conflict, remain contested and need more studies from different angles.

4. Role of state and ruling elites in state collapse and civil war

4.1. The main ideas of Bates and Reno

Bates and Reno explain the specific phenomenon of civil war which emerged in many of the sub-Saharan Africa countries in the late twentieth-century as a result of state collapse. Bates (2008) argues, using game theories, that political order is not a given. It only occurs when choices by rulers and citizens are in an equilibrium; the ruling elites, whom he regards as 'specialists in violence,' choose to being 'guardians' employing 'the means of coercion to protect the creation of wealth' (p. 5) and, at the same time, citizens 'choose to set weapons aside and to devote their time instead to the production of wealth and to the enjoyment of leisure' (p. 5). On the other hand, the political order collapses (and civil war emerges as a result) when this equilibrium is wavered; 'specialists in violence' turn from being 'guardians' to 'predators,' preying upon the wealth of the production of citizens, and citizens – reacting to this behaviour by their rulers – take up arms. In late-century Africa, the equilibrium was wavered, and thus states collapsed and civil war emerged. He argues that the essential root of the problems lies in the nature of the political manoeuvring and the policy choices of the ruling elites.

Bates nails down to the ruling elites' transformation of the state into an authoritarian regime as having ultimately increased the likelihood of the state collapse and civil war. The move occurred, according to Bates, due to the rulers' concerns over the cost of the provision of public goods,

including education. In post-independent Africa, in order for the incumbents to win the popular vote against challengers in elections and preserve their positions in office, they increasingly distributed material benefits in the form of public goods, including the provision of schooling. However, this practice became too expensive, and they decided to make the regime authoritarian. They prohibited the establishment of opposition parties and the holding of elections. The change allowed incumbents to be more 'predatory'; they retained more for themselves and distributed benefits as they liked, i.e. more narrowly and privately. Bates (2008) argues that this also meant that, for political opponents as well, promising and providing the constituency with services was no longer important. What they needed became the political favour of the ruling elites. Consequently, '[p]rivate benefits drove out public goods' (Bates, 2008, p. 52).

Bates (2008) also shows that the policy choices of the rulers themselves, albeit partly, contributed to their transformation to predators from being 'guardians.' They chose the main policy packages so-called 'control regimes', characterised by a centralised, closed and regulated economy. The package was economically devastating as well as costly, resulting in greatly decreased revenue. Bates (2008) claims, however, that 'control regimes' had unarguable political benefits for the ruling elites. One such benefit was being able to ease regional tensions that had been caused by the competition among regions for taking control of key industries in the country; the package put the industries under the direct control of the government. This also meant that, 'control regimes' increased the resources that were at the direct command of the president. At the same time, the decreased revenue represented a decline in the rewards from public service, i.e. protecting citizens, and as a result ruling elites turned to be predators. Reno (e.g. 2000, 2002, 2006) provides a different perspective with regards to why ruling elites chose the control regimes and made the state authoritarian. He places their security concerns as the primary factor. As local political elites and strongmen agitated for material benefits, ruling elites had to try hard to buy their loyalty or at least compliance through the provision of material benefits. If not, they could organise their followers to challenge the ruling elites. The most efficient, albeit short-term, measure was to distribute resources and assets to the key strongmen as patronage, rather than as public goods in a universal way. Reno (e.g. 2002) goes so far as to state that, 'From this perspective, expenditures on services like education and health care. . . would be wasted' (p. 840, emphasis added). Reno also argues that, out of fear, ruling elites chose the control regimes that they are equally aware that it would result in the weakening of state institutions. Indeed they wanted to weaken the institutions; if they are strong and services were provided well, those administrators who provide popular public services, such as security, education, and health, could acquire support from beneficiaries and then challenge the rulers. Regardless of the differences in the views about the motivations of the ruling elites, Bates and Reno show that weakening of state institutions has been directed by the political manoeuvres of the ruling elites. Such an academic explanation differs from the 'fragile states' discourse in the policy field, which partly argues that weak state institutions themselves facilitate, or even 'drive,' an emergence of violent conflict (e.g. Vallings and Moreno-Torres, 2005; DFID, 2005a,b; USAID, 2005). The point that weak state institutions are less capable of managing conflict non-violently finds agreement in some academic studies, including Stewart, Collier et al. and Bates (e.g. Stewart, 2000, 2008a; Collier and Rohner, 2008; Collier and Hoeffler, 2005; Bates, 2008). However, they do not regard weak state institutions as a cause of violent conflict.¹¹ They do not draw a causal relationship

¹¹ The fragile state discourse, for one, has a problem of endogeneity between 'fragile state' and violent conflict; it is common for indicators of fragile states to include the experience of conflict or political instability, and fragile states and conflict-affected countries tend to be treated together (e.g. DFID, 2005b; Rice and Patrick, 2008). Furthermore, the perspective merely focuses on the weakness of formal state institutions and misses out rulers' political manoeuvring outside formal institutions, more specifically in 'informal' markets (or the 'Shadow state' in Reno's (1995) words). They are considered as equally or more significant than that inside the formal institutions (Reno, 1995).

between regime types and civil war either, as some studies do (e.g. Hegre et al., 2001). It should be noted that a conclusive causality has not been drawn between a regime type and civil war.¹²

4.2. Ruling elites, the state and education Bates and Reno only briefly touch upon the role of education in their explanations. Their reference to education is limited to depicting it as one of the public goods the state used to provide but came to neglect. This happened partly by deliberately choosing policies that lowered public revenue, which as a result, weakened educational institutions and the capacity of the state to provide formal schooling. They do not portray educational institutions having an active role in the state collapse and consequent civil war, either. However, from Bates and Reno's explanations we may infer some features of the educational system that suggest that the ruling elites are becoming 'predators,' not 'guardians'. The explanations by Bates and Reno suggest that fundamentally the ruling elites' perception or conception of the provision of public goods and state institutions, including the education sector, had and can have direct consequences on the provision and the strength of the state institutions. The states was NOT weak from the beginning or lacking the finances and the capacity to provide education. However, the ruling elites chose to neglect the provision and weaken the institution deliberately because they saw that the provision of public goods was not a priority, but rather a 'waste'. They even saw as threatening to make the state institutions strong. These may not be written on paper but were shared by the ruling elites involved in the planning of the system and played and can play an important role. Although such intentions in the ruling elites may be difficult to infer and examine, the extent to which educational provision is provided in reality and how educational governance is run should suggest them to some degree. Also, from the citizens' point of view, they function as a barometer of the degree to which a government is committed to them (Burde, 2014) and to judge if rulers are being 'guardians' or 'predators.' Some argue that education is a key institution and service in judging the commitment of the government (Burde, 2014; Rose and Greeley, 2006); not only it is considered as a state responsibility in most contexts but also "it is the largest, most widespread and visible institution in the country, evident even in remote regions" (Rose and Greeley, 2006, p. 4). From the explanations of Bates and Reno, we may infer four 'symptoms' or features of governance of education – seeing it as one of the state institutions – which shows the ruling elites are functioning rather as 'predators' and, as a result, laying the foundation for civil war: (1) That decision-making power in education is centralised. Recall that, according to Bates, one of the primary tactics of the 'predators' was to make the state authoritarian. By doing so, the decision-making power was centralised to the rulers themselves, who were then able to concentrate state resources in their hands. (2) That accountability is absent or weak. In other words, there is no or little mechanism for stakeholders to assess the performances of the state and its institutions. The transformation of a state into an authoritarian one suggests that mechanisms to check and balance the power of ruling elites do not exist or are not functioning in practice. (3) That the capacity of state institutions is weak, and the provision of educational services is poor and/or neglected. Bates and Reno suggest that the ruling elites came to undermine their own state institutions and the provision of public services, including those of education. (4) The toleration and the prevalence of corruption that is based on systematic patronage, using public office for private benefits. Bates and Reno show that where there are no need to 'please' the general populace by making the state authoritarian, the ruling elites distribute the resources as patronage for their political benefits.

¹² Although it is widely accepted that civil wars happen in non-democratic states and "established democracies" rarely see them (Gleditsch and Hegre, 2014), democratic institutions on their own do not lead to less conflict; it is found to be contingent on the level of development (e.g. Hegre, 2003, 2014). Moreover, new democracies are shown to be politically unstable (e.g. Hegre et al. 2001). Other studies argue that anocracies or semidemocracies are susceptible to civil war, more than either pure democracies or pure dictatorship (e.g. Hegre et al., 2001), and yet the finding has been challenged due to the problematic use of the index (e.g. Vreeland, 2008).

These four symptoms were certainly apparent in the educational systems of cases that had experienced a civil war, including in Sierra Leone, where education has been much debated as part of the root causes of the war there (see Richards, 1996; Peters and Richards, 1998; Abdullah, 1998; Rashid, 2004). President Stevens centralised education as well as other state institutions under him (e.g. Banya, 1993), and expenditure on education declined drastically in the 1980s (Abdullah, 1998). Such that the system overall became dysfunctional by the early 1990s; dilapidated buildings, lack of essential school supplies, and closure of boarding schools were commonly observed (Banya, 1991). President Stevens intimidated those who opposed him while providing generous patronage to his ‘insiders.’ As such, corruption became rampant, including in the education system where teachers’ salaries were delayed for many months (Keen, 2005). The prevalent corruption and patrimonial politics was furthermore considered to be an important reason for the student radical group to start the ‘revolution,’ which evolved ultimately into the rebel group, Revolutionary United Front (RUF), that initiated the civil war.¹³ The students were frustrated that employment in public sector expected upon the completion of tertiary education was no longer available to them without having strong political connections (e.g. Krech and Maclure, 2003).

5. Discussion and conclusion

Through examining three distinct theoretical strands that explain the complex phenomena of contemporary violent conflict, I have explored in depth how education becomes part of the conditions that lay foundations for a conflict. We have seen how education can fuel people’s grievances, thereby raising a risk of violent conflict by analysing Stewart and Gurr’s theories; that is, the existence of educational HIs or education widening the gap between expectations and actual capabilities. However, it is also clarified that a sense of grievance towards education per se – either educational inequalities or the gap between expectations and actual capabilities – is not sufficient to spur a conflict. Educational grievance can do so when combined with other HIs, for Stewart, or, for Gurr, with pre-existing intense relative deprivation that is wide in scope in society. Moreover, Stewart’s idea of social significance elucidates that HIs in education only become relevant when education is perceived to or does in reality have social significance, and what is relevant is the HIs in the kind and the level of education that has social significance. From the explanations of Collier et al., we have seen that enrolling in school is one of the elements that increases the opportunity cost of rebellion, thereby contributing to reduce the likelihood of conflict. In other words, as a theory, it assumes that education is an element that increases the future economic opportunity, and what is relevant to the root cause of conflict is the level of education that does so or that is at least perceived to do so. On the other hand, Bates and Reno portray education as part of the political economy that surrounds the collapsing state; they show how education is part of the public services and state institutions the ruling elites come to neglect deliberately.

To extend the discussion, I focus on identifying the units of analysis that the exploration of the theories in this article have advanced and that should be examined in order to understand more comprehensively the ways in which education might be fuelling the root causes.¹⁴ First, through the exploration of Stewart’s theory, the article has refined ideas about the kinds of educational inequalities that are relevant to the risk of violent conflict. While educational literature has limited itself to show case by case how educational access was relevant to a conflict (see Matsumoto, 2015), it has become clear through Stewart’s theory when and what kind of inequalities can be relevant, as discussed above.

¹³ However, it is contentious whether the student radicals had stayed until the formation of the RUF or had abandoned before the RUF came to be formed (e.g. Abdullah, 1998; Rashid, 2004; Richards, 1996).

¹⁴ See Matsumoto (2015) for a detailed analysis of achievements and limitations of educational literature on the role of education in contemporary conflict, that are refereed in this section.

Second, I suggest the analysis of education at the level of beneficiaries, i.e. how the beneficiaries experience and perceive the education provided to them and what it does in their lives. While the majority of the studies in the educational literature in the area has been concerned with analysis of educational policies (see Matsumoto, 2015), the first two strands of theories explored in the article are concerned with why ordinary citizens take up arms, and they depict how education becomes a part of the reason citizens do so. Therefore it puts the focus on citizens or beneficiaries' perceptions and experiences of education, not education at policy levels. Gurr's idea of relative deprivation most strongly suggests this. As relative deprivation is about the gap between people's expectations and actual capabilities, it requires examination of what beneficiaries expect from education and what education actually enables them to do in their lives, as well as identifying if there is a gap between them. Stewart's theory also implies an analysis at the level of beneficiaries. For HIs in education to be relevant to the risk of conflict, the first condition is that education has social significance in the society in question. This requires an examination of what education is actually accomplishing in the lives of beneficiaries, in terms of their income or well-being (the actual social significance), as well as how beneficiaries perceive the social significance of education (social significance in perception).

The third unit of analysis that is inspired by the exploration of the theories is the conceptions or the representations of education. On the one hand, Bates and Reno show how the ruling elites conceive public services and state institutions (including education) as having direct effects on the extent to which services or institutions are neglected in failing states. Thus, how ruling elites perceive education as part of state institutions and public goods can be inferred as an important unit of analysis. On the other hand, 'representations' or expectations for the power of education held by the beneficiaries are essential too. Remember that, in Stewart's conception, educational inequalities become relevant to a risk of violent conflict when education has (or is perceived to have) social significance. While the actual social significance is covered by understanding education in context as above, the social significance of education in perception is essentially about what people 'expect' from education and whether it is the intrinsic or instrumental value of education that is perceived to have social significance. These are also important in understanding the actual social significance of education. By understanding the goals beneficiaries expect to reach by means of education, we can infer the level and type of education that actually enables them to achieve the goals. Not only Stewart but Gurr also clearly suggests the importance of understanding expectations on education; in the measures of relative deprivation, one of the two variables is people's expectations (against their actual capabilities).

Fourth, not only educational planning and written policies, – which have been analysed in the majority of cases in the educational literature (see Matsumoto, 2015) –, but actual implementations appear as important for analysis. As Bates and Reno show, in weak or failing states the extent to which state institutions function and public services are delivered – including the area of education – is not dependent on written policies as much as on the ruling elites' agendas. Thus, actual implementations may vary greatly from the written policies, and the implementations reveal more exactly the ruling elites' political agendas.

Lastly, educational governance is also an area to be explored more rigorously in understanding education's link to conflict. From the explanations of Bates and Reno, I have inferred four 'symptoms' or features of educational governance as a state institution of a country that manifests a risk of state collapse. To reiterate, (1) the centralisation of the decision-making power; (2) the absent or weak accountability; (3) the weak capacity of state institutions and poor/neglected provision of public services; (4) the toleration and the prevalence of corruption that is based on systematic patronage. Although the issues of educational governance have been taken up in educational studies and 'fragile states' related grey literature (e.g. UNESCO, 2008; Euro-Trends,

2009; Rose and Greeley, 2006), their links to a risk of conflict have not been discussed and they should be studied more rigorously.

The article has demonstrated the benefits of exploring three strands of explanations on the root causes of contemporary civil war. It has suggested ways in which the links of education to contemporary conflict in low-income and weak states can be explored more systematically and in relation to other conditions of society, which the educational literature in the area has been limited theoretically and conceptually.

The insights gained from the article are expected to be of more than academic interest. They caution against the tendency of development agencies to 'accept that education is generally benign and therefore that providing more education and greater access to schooling will be more benign' (Davies, 2005, p. 44). The tendency is represented by the 'Education for All' discourses that also affect the conflict affected and 'fragile' or weak states (Davies, 2005; Matsumoto, 2011). The article suggests that not only educational structure and curriculum on its own is conflict sensitive (Smith, 2005) in such fragile contexts, but also education in relation to other sectors and conditions in society needs to be conflict sensitive. After all, what matters is what education is doing to the lives of children and youths in such contexts, in particular, in creating socioeconomic opportunities for them. In order for education to achieve it, it may require a cross-sectoral collaboration among different social, economic and political sectors while strengthening a monitoring system to hold the ruling elites and the government accountable.

At the same time, it is clear from the article that more studies are necessary. A major limitation of the theories explored is that education is only lightly touched upon as one of the elements and is not rigorously examined or explored theoretically. To begin with, the validities of the theoretical suggestions regarding education need to be examined. There are also theories that the article did not explore, as mentioned at the beginning. In particular, the relationship between 'green war' theory, i.e. environmental scarcities, and education may be important to explore; this has fundamental relationships to the issues that are explored in the article, such as the population growth, the opportunity cost of conflict, and horizontal inequalities between haves and have-nots. Furthermore, although the article has limited the discussion to conflicts in sub-Saharan Africa, for the transnationalised conflicts of the kind we see in Syria and Iraq at the moment, a similar kind of work that analyses in depth root causes and education's relation to them are essential, as the nature of conflict might be changing quickly.

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